

Supplementary Figure 6. Flow cytometry and transcript analysis of C9 sub-clones vs. C9 PICs. (A) qRT-PCR transcript analysis of sub-clones (C9A-C) compared to C9 PICs. Bars represent the mean relative expression normalised to GAPDH. Error bars represent the standard deviation of the mean, n=3. (B) Flow cytometry histograms show consistent expression of Sca-1 and PW1 in sub-clones (C9A-C).